

DIDACTIC EDUCATIONAL TOOLS AS A FACTOR OF INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Annotation: This article describes the content of the pedagogical conditions for the use of modern didactic and technical means that have a positive impact on the effectiveness of the educational process in educational institutions, the development of creative thinking of students.

Keywords: education, process, tool, training, thinking, activity, technology, efficiency, result.

Pedagogy in the continuing education system and in society today profession is becoming the most prestigious and honorable profession. This, in turn, requires the involvement of experienced and talented pedagogues in the pedagogical process. In order to solve this urgent problem, i.e. training of personnel at the level of state educational standards requirements, pedagogues can only positively implement didactic process organization and objective management using modern teaching technology and audio-didactic and visual tools.

The teacher conducts the lessons using didactic tools organized by that is why it is envisaged to prepare and conduct lectures and practical exercises from didactic tools in classes in general secondary schools, and in professional education and higher education institutions. For this purpose, the curriculum, the content of the subject will be thoroughly studied, and electronic textbooks or manuals, virtual exhibitions, and didactic materials will be prepared. This is mainly aimed at explaining theoretical information, developing students' theoretical and technical thinking, arousing interest in the content of the course, and developing motives for preparing for the specialty is caught.

1. Preparation of training using didactic tools.

When applying a set of didactic tools in training sessions, in particular, it is recommended to use audiovisual tools in the following order:

- a) Preparation of didactic tools for training;
- b) preparing students to perceive didactic tool information;
- g) to display materials in the content of didactic tools short explanation of the teacher.
- d) information in didactic tools in the reader's memory organization of reinforcement;
- j) didactic tools, giving assignments at home to fill in information on the contents of the map, etc.

Also, technical tools, audio, video tools for the lesson when preparing, test them several times with an expert should consult and test the equipment. After making sure of this, you can begin to demonstrate the didactic tool.

b) in order to prepare students to understand the information of the didactic tool, first of all, before the didactic tool is shown, read the place of the information reflected in it in the system of the educational subject, curriculum, educational subject. It is necessary to comment on them to bring them to the attention of readers.

Thus, the teacher is a set of didactic tools for students always and all the time, as long as they are prepared in the perception of the content:

- educational topic with information in the content of the didactic tool integral unit of information;
- to prevent wrong assimilation of didactic tool information;
- deepening students' knowledge with the help of didactic tools, one should not forget issues such as expanding skills and qualifications.
- presentation of educational information using a didactic tool.

Modern virtual exhibitions are software products at least two people participate in its creation: the author of the content and the programmer.

One of the problems in creating a virtual exhibition is the mutual cooperation of the author and the programmer in making the author's work look like a computer program. The difficulty is that the author will not have a good idea about the possibilities of computer programs, and the programmer is not an expert in the subject of the textbook being created.

There are three different types of virtual exhibitions allocated to the program: Interactive demonstrations. In most cases, demonstration programs are computerized it cannot be a laboratory, because it will not have enough interactive

elements, but it can perform its functions according to the order of conducting experiments. In many cases, such programs can be a part of an electronic textbook as an additional tool for receiving educational material.

Simple models: The most common type. A simple model is usually an experiment will be a work model. Simple models combined according to some characteristics will be a set of experiments that will be a full-fledged virtual computer laboratory.

The widespread use of this type of laboratory, their creation easily, because one simple process written with one or two mathematical expressions is considered, and different laboratory works can be performed independently by different programmers. This approach is recommended for the creation of a small experimental course, when it is not necessary to create a universal system.

Universal laboratory: If in one experiment from its possibility's computer laboratories are truly universal if there is an opportunity to use them for experimenting with various phenomena. The creation of universal laboratories is carried out by a group of experienced programmers, in many cases using the modeling system related to scientific production as an experiment.

The characteristic of pedagogical technology is that it is placed in it an educational process that guarantees the achievement of goals is created and implemented. Teaching technology includes the following main elements:

- producing educational goals at a very precise level, selecting criteria for measuring and evaluating them;
- developing and clearly expressing the educational process aimed at achieving the educational goals;
- directing educational goals, the entire educational process, to the guaranteed achievement of educational results;
- immediately evaluate the results of training and make corrections in the training process;
- immediately evaluate the results of training and make corrections in the training process; final assessment of teaching results.

Thus, didactic in the course of theoretical and practical training the use of a set of tools, firstly, helps to form the educational didactic and technical thinking of students, to create the skills of working with modern technical tools; secondly, it provides practical support for filling the content of the studied subjects with the information required for the new era, for the formation of skills and qualifications for independent work with sources; thirdly, the set of didactic tools is wide for

training directs teachers-professors to use; fourthly, it ensures the development of students' memory, creative abilities, and physical fitness; fifth, educational process accelerates, strengthens the pedagogical foundations of perfection and, by realizing the principle of humanization of education, creates an opportunity to increase the spiritual and moral potential and professional skills of future specialists.

Therefore, the application of didactic teaching tools to the process of theoretical and practical training is the main task envisaged by the national personnel training program.

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